

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 5, Issue 3

2024

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№3 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2024-3>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель Совета
молодых ученых Отделения медицинских наук НАН Беларуси

ТАХРИЙИ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии
Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна
д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии
Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем
НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна
д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной
физикультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И.
Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич
д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины
Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-
Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедры ВОП №1,
Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич
д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических
методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич
д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской
оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины
государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии,
иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии,
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович

д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллович

д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олгиной Абдуганиевна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна

доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна

д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна

д.б.н, с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна

доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна

DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камильевна

к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович

к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна

доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна

доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна

PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманова Шоира Равшанбековна

Тошкент давлат стоматология институти госпитал терапевтик стоматология кафедраси доценти

Расулова Нодира Алишеровна

доцент кафедры педиатрии и общей практики ФПДО Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. O.S. Tirkashev, F.E. Matyakubova, N.T.Rabbimova, G.B. Mustaeva SPECIFIC CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS WITH HEMOCOLITIS SYNDROME IN EARLY CHILDHOOD.....	6
2. Djuraeva Kamola Stanislavovna, Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna MODERN ASPECTS OF WHOOPING COUGH.....	10
3. F.E. Matyakubova, G.B. Mustaeva, O.S. Tirkashev, N.T.Rabbimova STUDY OF CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS IN PREGNANT WOMEN.....	16
4. Ibadov Ravshan Aliyevich, Ibragimov Sardor Khamdamovich, Ergashev Sukhrob Panji oʻgli THE IMPACT OF PREOPERATIVE COVID-19 INFECTION ON EARLY POSTOPERATIVE RESULTS IN MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT.....	23
5. O.S. Tirkashev, F.E. Matyakubova, N.T.Rabbimova, G.B. Mustaeva SPECIFIC CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE INTESTINAL INFECTIONS WITH HEMOCOLITIS SYNDROME IN EARLY CHILDHOOD.....	31
6. Эльнора А. Абдуганиева, Ирина В. Ливерко, Шахбосхон М. Ахмедов, Юлия Э. Фаттахова, Шоира Г. Матрзаева, Дильноза М. Халилова РОЛЬ ГИПЕРКОАГУЛЯЦИОННЫХ СОСТОЯНИЙ КАК ОСНОВНОЙ ПРИЧИНЫ ФАТАЛЬНЫХ ИСХОДОВ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ОБСТРУКТИВНОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ ЛЕГКИХ.....	35
7. N.T.Rabbimova, F.E. Matyakubova, O.S. Tirkashev, G.B. Mustaeva THE ROLE OF S. PNEUMONIAE IN EXCERNATION OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE.....	40
8. Djuraeva Kamola Stanislavovna, Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna MODERN ASPECTS OF WHOOPING COUGH.....	46
9. Eshonkhodjaev Otabek Djuraevich, Rakhimiy Sharif Uktamovich MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MEDISTINAL TUMORS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	52
10. Najmutdinova D.K., Nasirova A.K., Rasulov A.D. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS AND VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION...	60

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

Djuraeva Kamola Stanislavovna

Assistant

Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna

PhD, Associate Professor

Department of Infectious Diseases

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

e- mail: djuraevakamola1988@gmail.ru

MODERN ASPECTS OF WHOOPING COUGH

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235473>

ANNOTATION

Available data indicate that whooping cough remains an important disease in infancy and childhood, especially among those who have not received adequate immunization. Over the past 15 years, successful immunization programs have been implemented in most countries of the world. Despite high levels of vaccination coverage, pertussis remains an important cause of childhood morbidity and mortality worldwide. There is an epidemic of whooping cough in many countries around the world, and a significant proportion of the sick people are vaccinated people. **Goal of the work.** The purpose of the work is to analyze specialized scientific literature to summarize data and present a modern view on the issues of etiology, epidemiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, diagnosis, treatment and immunoprophylaxis of whooping cough. **Material and methods.** A review of publications by domestic and foreign authors, clinical recommendations for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of whooping cough was carried out, and data from randomized clinical and epidemiological studies were studied. **Results and its discussion.** Modern data on the epidemiology of whooping cough, features of its clinical manifestations, diagnosis and treatment in different age groups are presented. **Conclusions.** The increase in incidence is possibly due to changes in the structure of the pathogen, changes in the duration of the incubation period, a decrease in vaccination coverage, as well as the use of more sensitive laboratory diagnostic methods. At the time of the study, it was revealed that severe and complicated forms of whooping cough are typical for children in the first months of life. Numerous epidemiological measures and the use of modern diagnostic methods have led to a reduction in the duration and severity of clinical manifestations and limit the spread of infection. At the moment, it is necessary to improve the whooping cough vaccination strategy, maintain a high level of vaccination coverage and strictly observe anti-epidemic measures in the foci of infection.

Key words: infants, pertussis, epidemiology, immunization, diagnosis.

Джураева Камола Станиславовна

АССИСТЕНТ

Эргашева Муниса Якубовна

PhD, доцент

Кафедра инфекционных болезней
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан
e-mail: djuraevakamola1988@gmail.ru

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ КОКЛЮША

АННОТАЦИЯ

Имеющиеся данные показывают, что коклюш остается важным заболеванием в младенчестве и детстве, особенно среди тех, кто не получил адекватной иммунизации. За последние 15 лет успешные программы иммунизации были реализованы в большинстве стран мира. Несмотря на высокий уровень охвата вакцинацией, коклюш остается важной причиной детской морбидности и летальности во всем мире. Во многих странах мира идет эпидемия коклюша, причем значительную долю среди заболевших составляют привитые люди. **Цель работы** - проанализировать специализированную научную литературу для обобщения данных и представить современный взгляд на вопросы этиологии, эпидемиологии, патогенеза, клинических проявлений, диагностики, лечения и иммунопрофилактики коклюша. **Материал и методы.** Проведен обзор публикаций отечественных и зарубежных авторов, клинических рекомендаций по диагностике, лечению и профилактике коклюша, изучены данные рандомизированных клинических и эпидемиологических исследований. **Результаты и их обсуждение.** Представлены современные данные об эпидемиологии коклюша, особенностях его клинических проявлений, диагностики и лечения в разных возрастных группах. **Выводы.** Рост заболеваемости возможно связан с изменениями в структуре возбудителя, изменениями продолжительности инкубационного периода, снижением охвата вакцинацией, а также использованием более чувствительных методов лабораторной диагностики. На момент исследования выявлено, что тяжелые и осложненные формы коклюша характерны для детей первых месяцев жизни. Проведенные многочисленные эпидемиологические мероприятия и использование современных методов диагностики привели к уменьшению длительности и тяжести клинических проявлений и ограничению распространения инфекции. На данный момент необходимо совершенствовать стратегию вакцинации от коклюша, поддерживать высокий уровень охвата вакцинацией и четко соблюдать противоэпидемические мероприятия в очагах инфекции.

Ключевые слова: младенцы, коклюш, эпидемиология, иммунизация, диагностика.

Whooping cough is an acute respiratory disease caused by *B. pertussis*, the main manifestation of which is a paroxysmal cough. Despite vaccine advances, pertussis remains a significant cause of childhood morbidity and mortality and a major public health problem worldwide. According to WHO, about 60 million people worldwide fall ill with whooping cough every year and about 1 million children die, mostly under the age of one year [1]. Currently, in many countries of the world (USA, Australia, the Netherlands, Canada, etc.), despite the high vaccination coverage of the child population, there is an epidemic of whooping cough

The age structure of cases is dominated by children under 1 year of age. Most of the sick people were not vaccinated.

The increase in whooping cough incidence rates, according to scientists, may be associated with various reasons: the use of more sensitive research methods, changes in the antigenic structure of the pathogen, the insufficient effectiveness of modern vaccines and the short duration of post-vaccination immunity, a decrease in vaccination coverage, etc. [12,8,5].

Adolescents and adults are the main source of outbreaks and infection in families of infants who are unvaccinated, in whom whooping cough is very severe and poses a direct threat to life [9,2,10]. Transmission of the infection occurs through airborne droplets and is only possible through close contact with a patient or carrier. Vaccinated people can be carriers of the whooping cough pathogen and participate in the epidemic process, spreading the infection. Infectivity index ranges from 0,7 to 1,0. An autumn-winter rise in incidence with a peak in December-January is typical [11].

Currently, whooping cough in unvaccinated people retains all its typical manifestations. The incubation period ranges from 3 to 14 days.

The onset of the disease is gradual with increasing dynamics of dry cough (catarrhal period, duration 1-2 weeks), while there are no symptoms of intoxication, fever, and the patients' well-being is slightly impaired. As a rule, at this stage, patients are diagnosed with ARVI. Next, the cough becomes paroxysmal (the period of spasmodic cough), which lasts from 1 to 6 weeks. A coughing attack with whooping cough consists of a series of short coughing impulses on exhalation, followed by intense inhalation, which is accompanied by a whistling sound (reprise).

During an attack, the patient's face turns red or becomes cyanotic, the neck veins swell, the eyes water, the tongue protrudes from the mouth and is curled upward.

The attack ends with the discharge of viscous, glassy sputum or vomiting. Vomiting after a coughing attack is very characteristic of whooping cough. Whooping cough cough worsens at night, after physical or emotional stress. The number of coughing attacks during the day ranges from single to 40-50 or more. The patient's condition between coughing attacks may not be disturbed (except for severe forms of the disease), which can confuse the doctor in assessing his condition.

The convalescence phase of whooping cough lasts several weeks and is characterized by a gradual decrease in the frequency and intensity of cough.

In adolescents and adults, whooping cough often occurs in atypical forms and is manifested by a prolonged cough, for which they usually receive ineffective therapy from general practitioners, allergists and otolaryngologists. However, even in these age groups, whooping cough can have a typical course and be complicated by pneumonia (2%), urinary incontinence (28%), collapse (6%), rib fractures (4%), etc. [4]. It should be noted that there is "insufficient alertness" regarding whooping cough among doctors in the "adult" network, and therefore the diagnosis in adults is often made in the later stages of the disease.

Whooping cough is most relevant for infants. Most cases of death and severe disease develop in children in the first months of life. Children less than 2 months of age have an increased risk of death. The high-risk group for the development of adverse outcomes includes premature babies, children with intrauterine growth retardation, pathology of the central nervous system, respiratory system and heart. In infants, whooping cough occurs with a short catarrhal period, a longer period of spasmodic cough (up to 2 months), and there may be no recurrences. Coughing attacks may result in apnea. Encephalopathy may develop, which is manifested by loss of consciousness, convulsions, paralysis or paresis of the limbs. According to the literature, in the period from 1997 to 2000, 7203 cases of whooping cough in children in the first six months of life were registered in the United States. Of these, 63,1% of children were hospitalized, 11,8% developed pneumonia, 1,4% had seizures, 0,2% had encephalopathy, and 0,8% of children died [5]. Deaths were mainly associated with the development of severe pneumonia, pulmonary hypertension, encephalopathy and multiple organ failure. Children with leukocytosis greater than $50\ 000 \times 10^9 / l$ have a 10 times higher risk of death. Rare complications of whooping cough include pneumothorax, emphysema, subarachnoid and intraventricular hemorrhages, subdural and epidural hematomas, lingual frenulum ulcer, rupture of the diaphragm, umbilical and inguinal hernia, rectal prolapse, severe alkalosis and associated tonic convulsions, dehydration [13].

Diagnosis of whooping cough is based on epidemiological and clinical laboratory data.

All patients who have been coughing for more than 7 days are subject to mandatory laboratory testing for whooping cough (2 times bacteriological and/or 1 time polymerase chain reaction). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) has high sensitivity and is currently the most common method for diagnosing whooping cough.

Bacteriological and PCR studies for whooping cough are recommended to be carried out during the first 3 weeks of the disease. In clinically unclear cases, with negative results of bacteriological and PCR studies, late stages of the disease and in vaccinated people, a 2-fold serological examination with an interval of 10-14 days by ELISA is recommended. Confirmation of the clinical diagnosis of "whooping cough" in unvaccinated patients is a single detection of specific IgM and/or IgA and/or IgG (ELISA), or antibodies in a titer of 1/80 or more (RA). In vaccinated

people, whooping cough is indicated by an increase or decrease of 4 or more times in the level of specific IgG and/or IgA (ELISA), or the level of antibodies (RA) when examining paired sera taken at an interval of at least 2 weeks. Hematological changes (leukocytosis with lymphocytosis and normal ESR) are of great diagnostic and prognostic importance for whooping cough.

In the treatment of whooping cough, great importance is given to routine measures. Long walks in the fresh air and a protective regime are recommended. Infants are subject to hospitalization regardless of the severity of the disease; patients with severe and complicated forms of whooping cough; children with concomitant pathology (perinatal encephalopathy, convulsive syndrome, prematurity, malnutrition of II-III degree, congenital heart disease, bronchial asthma). According to epidemic indications, children from “closed groups” (orphanages, camps, dormitories, etc.) are hospitalized. Children with apnea, seizures, or respiratory failure should be hospitalized in the intensive care unit.

All patients with suspected whooping cough should begin etiotropic therapy without waiting for examination results. The drugs of choice are macrolides. Azithromycin is prescribed 10 mg/kg per day as a single dose for 5 days. In children over 6 months, a clarithromycin suspension can be prescribed at a dose of 7,5 mg/kg per os within 7 days. Macrolides may prevent or reduce the clinical manifestations of whooping cough if they are used during the incubation period or in the early catarrhal stage. During the paroxysmal phase of the disease, antimicrobial drugs do not change the clinical course, but may eliminate bacteria from the nasopharynx and thus reduce their transmission. If macrolides are contraindicated, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole can be prescribed. In severe forms of the disease, the use of 3rd generation cephalosporins is recommended. Antibiotics are most effective when prescribed early in the disease. In the treatment of whooping cough, non-narcotic antitussive drugs (butamirate) are used. For severe whooping cough, mechanical ventilation, oxygen therapy and hormonal therapy (dexamethasone, prednisolone) are performed. There is evidence of the effectiveness of double exchange blood transfusion and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation in severe forms.

Anti-epidemic measures consist of isolating the patient. Patients with whooping cough are isolated for 25 days from the onset of the disease. Contact children under the age of 14 years who have a cough, regardless of vaccination history, are subject to exclusion from attending preschool educational and general education organizations until they receive two negative bacteriological results and/or one negative PCR test result. In family units, contact children are placed under medical supervision for 14 days. Prevention of whooping cough in children in the first months of life involves preventing contact with any “coughing” patients.

Newborns in maternity hospitals, children in the first three months of life and unvaccinated children under 1 year of age who have had contact with a patient with whooping cough are injected intramuscularly with normal human immunoglobulin. After isolating the patient, all contacts are recommended to take macrolides for 7 days in an age-appropriate dosage.

Prevention through vaccination remains the most effective means of protection against whooping cough. Vaccination begins at the age of three months and consists of three injections of adsorbed pertussis-diphtheria-tetanus vaccine with an interval of 1,5 months. Revaccination is carried out 1,5-2 years after the course of vaccination.

Adsorbed pertussis-diphtheria-tetanus vaccine is a whole-cell vaccine and consists of a suspension of killed pertussis microbes and purified tetanus and diphtheria toxoids adsorbed on aluminum hydroxide. For vaccination against whooping cough, the whole-cell Tetracok vaccine (an adsorbed vaccine for the prevention of diphtheria, tetanus, whooping cough and polio) is also used. Vaccination with whole-cell vaccines is contraindicated if the child has a progressive pathology of the nervous system, a history of afebrile seizures, complications or a strong general reaction (increase in temperature in the first two days to 40°C or higher) to the previous administration of the vaccine. Currently, acellular (cell-free) vaccines are widely used to prevent whooping cough, which are less likely to cause side effects. Acellular vaccines include: “Infanrix” (a vaccine for the prevention of whooping cough, diphtheria and tetanus), “Pentaxim” (a combination vaccine containing adsorbed acellular pertussis-diphtheria-tetanus vaccine, inactivated polio vaccine and a vaccine for the

prevention of *Haemophilus influenzae* infection), “Infanrix HEXA”(recombinant vaccine for the prevention of whooping cough, diphtheria, tetanus, polio, *Haemophilus influenzae* infection, viral hepatitis B). Vaccination against whooping cough in most cases prevents the disease, however, 3-5 or more years after vaccination, the intensity of post-vaccination immunity decreases, and those vaccinated may become ill. Whooping cough in vaccinated people occurs predominantly in a mild form, specific complications develop 4 times less frequently than in unvaccinated people, and no deaths are observed. In the USA and most European countries, vaccination against whooping cough begins at 2 months of age; in preschool age, a 2nd revaccination with an acellular vaccine is carried out, and adolescents and adults, including pregnant women, are also vaccinated.

Thus, at present, despite high vaccination coverage, there is a significant increase in the incidence of whooping cough in children and adults around the world. In connection with the current epidemic situation, it is necessary to improve the vaccination strategy against whooping cough, maintain high coverage of timely vaccination and revaccination against whooping cough in children, strictly observe anti-epidemic measures in the foci of infection, and widely use modern methods of laboratory diagnosis of whooping cough in all patients with prolonged cough.

References:

1. Bettiol S, Wang K, Thompson MJ et al. Symptomatic treatment of the cough in whooping cough. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2012; 5 (CD003257).
2. Bisgard KM, Pascual FB, Ehresmann KR et al. Infant pertussis: who was the source. *Pediatr Infect Dis J.* 2004; 23: 985–989.
3. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Pertussis (Whooping Cough), Clinicians, Clinical Complications. 2012; Available at: <http://www.cdc.gov/pertussis/clinical/features.html>
4. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Pertussis-United States, 1997–2000. *MMWR.* 2002; 51 (4): 73.
5. Cherry JD. Why do pertussis vaccines fail. *Pediatrics.* 2012; 129: 968–970.
6. Gosudarstvennyj doklad o sostojanii sanitarno-jepidemiologicheskogo blagopoluchija naselenija v Rossijskoj Federacii v 2014 godu [State report about the state sanitary and epidemiological welfare of the population in the Russian Federation in 2014]. M: Federal Supervision Agency for Customer Protection and Human Welfare. 2015; 206 p.
7. Juraeva N. et al. Analysis of the clinical effectiveness of cycloferon and polyoxidonium in women of reproductive age with brucellosis. – 2022.
8. Liko J, Steve G. Robison. Priming with whole-cell versus acellular pertussis vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2013; 7: 581–582.
9. Lapij FI. Aktual'nost' jeffektivnoj zashhity protiv kokljusha [The rationale of effective protection against pertussis]. *Zdorov'e rebenka [Child health].* 2010; 3: 86.
10. Lobzin YV, Bakhareva NV. Retrospective Study of the Clinical Epidemiological Characteristics of Pertussis in Infants Prior to Their First Vaccination in the Russian Federation. *Infect Dis Ther.* 2015; 4 (1): 113–123.
11. Sizemov AN, Komeleva EV Kokljush: klinika, diagnostika, lechenie [Pertussis: clinical findings, diagnosis, treatment]. *Lechashhij vrach [Doctor in charge].* 2005; 7: 82–87 .
12. Tatochenko VK. Kokljush - nedoupravljaemaja infekcija [Pertussis - uncontrolled infection]. *Voprosy sovremennoj pediatrii [Questions of current pediatrics].* 2014; 13(2): 78–82.
13. Theilen U, Johnston ED, Robinson PA. Rapidly fatal invasive pertussis in young infants show can we change the outcome. *BMJ.* 2008; 27: 337– 343.
14. Yarmukhamedova N. A. et al. Modern aspects and role of the cytokine status of the problem of brucellosis Abstract //International Scientific and Practical conference “COVID-19 and other topical infections of Central Asia” June 23-24, 2022, Shymkent. – 2022. – P. 172.

15. Clinical-epidemiological characteristics of mumps infection in children and adolescents in Samarkand region. N.A.Yarmukhamedova, O.S.Tirkashev, N.S.Yakubova, K.S.Dzhurayeva . Problem biology and medicine . 2018.-#2. 152-154.
16. Clinical and epidemiological transmission of scarlet fever diseases and criteria for diagnosis. Matnazarova G.S Tirkashev O.S, Mustayeva G.B Central asian journal of medical and natural sciences May-June 2021 ISSN: 2660 – 4159 (166-169 pages).
17. Specific clinical-laboratory characteristics of acute intestinal infections with hemocolitis syndrome in early-aged children. Tirkashev OS, Mustaeva GB, Oralov JB Science and education scientific journal, volume 5, issue 2 Feb. - 2024 (p. 125-129)

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000